

DIELECTRIC BEHAVIOR AND THERMO-MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF BaTiO₃ REINFORCED AND CARBON REINGORCED EPOXY COMPOSITES

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1 General Introduction

Polymer composites incorporating ferroelectric and piezoelectric particles, randomly distributed within the polymer matrix, are considered as a novel class of engineering materials. The electrical response of these hybrid materials can be suitably adjusted by controlling the type and the amount of the ceramic inclusions. Modern electronic devices require new high dielectric permittivity materials with enhanced dielectric strength [1-3]. These materials are expected to address the engineering demands for suitable dielectric properties and exhibit improved mechanical strength and ease processing at a relative low cost. Ceramic-polymer composites can be used in various applications including integrated capacitors, acoustic emission sensors, smart skins and leakage current controllers [1-4].

In this study, ceramic fillers and carbon materials are used as epoxy reinforcements resulting in composites with enhanced dielectric, electrical, and thermo-mechanical properties. The carbon fillers used are carbon black [CB], vapor grown carbon fibers [VGCF] and exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets [xGnP]. Possible synergy on the composites performance between ceramic and carbon fillers is also investigated by fabricating and characterizing composites containing both ceramic and carbon fillers at various ratios.

2 Experimental

2.1 Materials

The polymer used is a low viscosity epoxy resin with the trade name Araldite LY 564 and curing agent Aradur-HY2954 both provided by Huntsman Advanced Materials. The ceramic reinforcement is BaTiO₃ powder of two sizes. One with mean particle diameter less than 2 μm and another with mean particle diameter in the range of 30-50 nm both

supplied by Sigma Aldrich. The carbon fillers used are: i) nano-size high structure carbon black (CB) with mean particle diameter in the range of 40-50 nm (KETJENBLACK EC-600 JD), provided by Akzo Novel Polymer Chemicals LLC, ii) vapor grown carbon fibers (VGCF) with mean particle diameter less than 150 nm (Pyrograf III, PR-19 PS grade), supplied by Pyrograf Products, Inc., and iii) exfoliated graphite nanoplatelets (xGnP-1) with mean particle diameter less than 0.1 μm and an average thickness of 10-20 nm supplied by XG Sciences (East Lansing, MI).

2.2 Fabrication of Composites

The dispersion of the BaTiO₃ in the epoxy took place in a dissolver device (VMA Getzmann GmbH). The compound was stirred in a vacuum container to avoid air entrapment. During processing the temperature was increased up to 60 °C to facilitate the filler wetting by the epoxy. The compound was placed in a sonic bath for 20 min to enhance further the dispersion quality by breaking any remaining agglomerations. The above process was used to produce a BaTiO₃-epoxy master-batch compound with a content of 20 phr (filler parts per hundred epoxy parts) BaTiO₃. Dilution down to 5 and 10 phr was used to produce composites with different filler content. Both sizes of BaTiO₃ powder were used. The filler-epoxy solution was purred in to a mold and cured at T=80 °C for 1 hour followed by post curing at T=100 °C for 4 hours.

Alternatively, a second fabrication method was used. In order to avoid agglomeration the filler powder (ceramic or carbon) was mixed with isopropyl alcohol (IPA) using a sonication probe (misonix 4000) for 40 minutes at 40% amplitude. The agglomerate free powder, collected after the removal of IPA through filtration, was mixed at room temperature with the proper amount of monomer

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using sonication. The curing agent was added to the filler-monomer solution and mixing continued for 10 min. The mixture was degassed in a vacuum oven, cast in a mold and cured at $T=80\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 hour followed by post curing at $T=100\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 4 hours.

2.3 Characterization of Composites

The electrical characterization of the composites was conducted by means of Broadband Dielectric Spectroscopy (BDS) in the frequency range of 0.1 Hz to 10MHz, using Alpha-N Frequency Response Analyser and a 1200 BDS dielectric cell provided by Novocontrol. Isothermal frequency scans were conducted, for each specimen, from ambient temperature to $160\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ with a step of $10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. Novotherm system supplied by Novocontrol was used to control the temperature. Other properties that were examined are crystalline structure of the ceramic powders using X-ray diffraction to detect the transition from the non symmetrical polar to cubic non-polar structure of BaTiO₃. This was done using D8 Advance (Bruker AXS) with a CuK α (1.54 angstrom) source and 1.6 kW power.

The viscoelastic properties, including storage and loss modulus and tan delta, of the composites were determined using a Dynamic Mechanical Analyzer (DMA, Q800, TA Instruments). The specimens were characterized using single-cantilever mode as a function of temperature (30 to $160\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, heating rate $5\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$). A constant force of 100 mN was applied at frequency of 1 Hz.

Finally the composites morphology was investigated using scanning electron microscopy (SEM, Leo Supra 35VP) for presence of voids and agglomerates, and the state of filler dispersion within the polymer matrix.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Dielectric Properties

BaTiO₃ is chosen as the ceramic filler because of its unique characteristic to change its crystalline structure in a controllable and reversible manner. The cubic structure (paraelectric phase), shown in Figure 1a (left) is present at high temperatures whereas the tetragonal crystalline structure (ferroelectric phase) is present at lower temperatures. The temperature at which this transition occurs is the Curie temperature, T_c , and it's a characteristic of the material. Based on X-ray

diffraction, the crystalline structure depends also on the particle size. As shown in Figure 1b, the transition between the two structures is detected for the micro-sized BaTiO₃ particles only which exhibit a tetragonal structure at $T=40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ whereas their structure is cubic at $T=170\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. It is noted that $T_c=130\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$. The nano-sized BaTiO₃ exhibits hybrid cubic/tetragonal structure at all temperatures.

Fig. 1. a) Schematic of the crystalline structure of BaTiO₃ (cubic on the left and tetragonal on the right) and b) X-ray diffraction spectra of BaTiO₃ as a function of particle size and temperature.

In addition to the transition between the two structures, BaTiO₃ is used as filler because it is a piezoelectric and ferroelectric material. The ability to utilize these unique properties of BaTiO₃ can lead to responsive (smart) materials and enable many technological applications.

The real part of dielectric permittivity of BaTiO₃/epoxy composites, made by the first compounding method, and measured at $T=70\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ is shown in Figure 2 as a function of frequency, particle size and concentration. The following observations can be made i) all the composites have higher ϵ' values than the epoxy, ii) the micro size composite shows higher values than the nano-size

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and iii) the lowest nano-size filler concentration increases ϵ' more than the higher concentrations do, because the higher the particle concentration the less homogeneous the dispersion and the higher the probability of agglomerates. The increase of the permittivity upon addition of BaTiO₃ is expected because the ceramic filler is a wide band semiconducting material.

Fig. 2. The real part of dielectric permittivity of BaTiO₃/epoxy composites versus frequency.

The permittivity of the epoxy and BaTiO₃/epoxy composites as a function of temperature, filler loading, and particle size for constant frequency of 1 Hz is shown in Figure 3. As indicated addition of fillers increases the permittivity which however, remains constant with temperature for low temperatures. However, there is a temperature regime, 115 to 140 °C for which a sudden increase in permittivity is observed. This change is a result of the relaxations modes of the epoxy used. This is further investigated by studying the viscoelastic properties of the epoxy.

It is also noted that the increase in permittivity is higher for the micro-size BaTiO₃ particles. Considering also that these larger particles exhibit the transition from tetragonal to cubic crystalline structure as shown in Figure 1, it is concluded that micro-size BaTiO₃ is a very promising candidate for the development of tunable dielectric materials.

A comparison between the electrical permittivity of BaTiO₃/epoxy and xGnP/epoxy composites at frequency of 1Hz as a function of temperature is presented in Figure 4. The composites are made

using the second compounding method. As shown addition of BaTiO₃ has no significant effect on the permittivity of neat epoxy. A small increase is only observed at higher temperatures and high filler loadings. On the contrary, addition of xGnP, even at low concentrations, dramatically increases the permittivity throughout the temperature regime studied. The high electrical conductivity and anisotropy of xGnP, as well as the enhanced electrical heterogeneity of the system, which gives rise to interfacial polarization effect, could be considered as responsible for the observed behavior.

Fig. 3. The real part of dielectric permittivity of BaTiO₃/epoxy composites as a function of temperature

Fig. 4. The real part of dielectric permittivity of BaTiO₃/epoxy and xGnP/PP composites as a function of temperature at constant frequency of 1Hz

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It is also observed that there is a change in the slope of the permittivity-temperature curves for the neat epoxy and both types of composites studied. This change occurs at about $T=130^{\circ}\text{C}$ which is close to the Curie temperature. The fact that the transition is present even in case of the neat epoxy and the xGnP composites indicates that it is not related to the T_c transition of the ceramic filler. To investigate this further, the viscoelastic properties of the epoxy and the composites were also studied.

The tan delta of the epoxy and the composite systems determined as a function of temperature for constant frequency of 1 Hz is shown in Figure 5. It is observed that the glass transition temperature, T_g , of the epoxy defined as the peak of the tan delta curve is about 130°C which coincides with the T_c of the ceramic filler.

Fig. 5. Tan delta of BaTiO₃/epoxy and xGnP/PP composites as a function of temperature at constant frequency of 1Hz

In addition to the dielectric and viscoelastic properties of these composites, their mechanical properties were also characterized. The flexural modulus and strength of the ceramic and graphite reinforced epoxy composites is shown in Figure 6a and 6b respectively. As indicated, the modulus increases upon addition of fillers especially in case of xGnP. However, the strength of the epoxy decreases in presence of either filler indicating existence of agglomerates and inhomogeneous dispersion of the filler within the epoxy matrix which results in weak filler/epoxy interactions and poor load transfer.

Fig. 6. Flexural a) modulus and b) strength of BaTiO₃/epoxy and xGnP/epoxy composites

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